

Recommended citation: Pälviö, T., Ahonen, M., & Schrey-Niemenmaa, K. (2018). Students' View about Development of an Electric Tool for Self-evaluation of Engineering Education as thesis project. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1134-1142). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672810.

Students' View about Development of an Electronic Tool for Self-evaluation of Engineering Education as Thesis project

T Pälviö

Student

Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
Helsinki, Finland

E-mail: tommi.palvio@nic.fi

M Ahonen

Student

Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
Helsinki, Finland

E-mail: miika.ahonen@metropolia.fi

K Schrey-Niemenmaa¹

Senior Lecturer

Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
Helsinki, Finland

E-mail: katriina.schrey@metropolia.fi

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Innovation as the context for Engineering Education

Keywords: students view of education, quality, real life projects, IT development

¹ Corresponding Author
K. Schrey-Niemenmaa
Katriina.schrey@metropolia.fi

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to give an overview of a student driven project that had the goal of designing and implementing a user-friendly application for managing e-form based surveys. The application was designed to be used as an electronical tool in an ongoing project exploring a practical approach to quality assurance through continuous self-evaluation and cross-sparring. Publicly available survey management tools did not provide the support for result analysis in the way that was needed in the project, which is why the clients wanted to develop a tool that was designed specifically for the needs of the project.

The task was undertaken by two final year students as a thesis project. The project was carried out in close cooperation with the clients, and feedback from the clients was utilized throughout the development process. The application was developed using modern web technologies and currently relevant frameworks to speed up the development. The paper will focus on covering the methodology used in the project as well as the application design.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1.1 Node.js platform

Node.js is a popular JavaScript runtime that is widely used as a server-side platform to run JavaScript based web applications. The runtime is based on Google's V8 JavaScript engine, and it utilizes non-blocking event-driven architecture with the single threaded programming model. [1.] Node.js is different from other web development platforms for it can create its own server to handle requests and serve static files, and therefore programs written for the platform are not necessarily dependent on a separate server layer such as the Apache server [2].

One reason for the high popularity of Node is its capability to handle requests quickly, which has made it a preferable platform for fast and scalable web applications. The architecture the platform is based on makes it possible to run operations asynchronously so that slower operations do not significantly impair the performance of the whole application. [1; 3.]

1.2 Frameworks

Instead of just adding additional functionality to an application like modules and libraries, frameworks generally function as a foundation for an application. There are different kind of frameworks and some of them only provide a layout for the developers to build upon, whereas so called full-stack frameworks define entirely the technical implementation of an application. [4.]

In web development, frameworks can be split into frontend and backend frameworks. Backend framework is a component of the server side that is usually involved in the process of request handling. Frontend framework is part of browser side that usually affects how a web page is rendered and how it reacts to user interaction. [4.]

1.3 Sails framework

Sails is a backend framework for Node.js platform. Sails is built upon Express framework and it consists of multiple smaller modules. Sails contains large amount of functionality in itself, and it defines strict conventions for the development. Due to the enforced guidelines, the development with Sails is straightforward and the framework is considered to be highly user friendly. A major feature of Sails is that it makes it possible to utilize multiple different database solutions simultaneously with a Sails application by supporting relations between database models stored in different types of databases. With Sails database models are defined as

separate modules by specifying the attributes and model relations. The system allows for extensive customization of a model, and the database library will enforce the defined schema, and update or create a database table accordingly to match it. [4.]

1.4 Koa framework

Koa is backend framework based on Express developed by the same people, and it uses JavaScript generators to define middleware functions. Koa is minimalistic framework that is essentially a middleware-based HTTP (hypertext transfer protocol) server library. Generator syntax allows the code to be written in almost synchronous style which makes writing callback dependent middleware simpler and the code more readable. Suggested use cases for Koa include lightweight web applications and HTTP APIs (application programming interface). [4.]

2 SYSTEM DESIGN

2.1 Overview of the application

The application is an e-form based survey management tool, for managing, running and analyzing the results of surveys through a web client. The application is designed specifically for the surveys of the self-evaluation system used by the clients, but it can be used to run practically any kinds of surveys. The self-evaluation system used in the project is based on a specific set of questions and the statistics gained by comparing the answers of different answerer groups.

The questions of the self-evaluation system are multidimensional, meaning that the questions are evaluated using multiple sub questions that are also called criteria. A typical question of the system would be to evaluate the urgency and importance of an issue. In this case the issue is the question, and the urgency and importance are criteria used to evaluate the issue.

The flow of the application is such that users are expected to login or register to the application in order to gain access to all of its features. In addition to creating and answering surveys, users are able to manage groups and evaluations that are used in specifying a target group for a survey. The application offers a graphical representation of the results of survey, and additionally the results can be downloaded as a separate file.

Each user of the application is attached to a group or groups that represent the user's background, like for example whether a user is a student or a teacher. Answers to a survey are grouped based on the answerers' groups, so that the answers immediately reflect the discrepancies between each group's answers. The target group of a survey is defined by so called evaluation group that consists of multiple user groups. Evaluation groups can be used multiple times, making it simple to run multiple surveys with the same target group.

To make recreating a survey simple, surveys can be saved as templates for future use. When creating a new survey, user can select any existing template as foundation for the survey so that all the questions of the template will be immediately available in the new survey. All the questions attached to templates are also separately available for importing when editing an existing survey.

Answering to a survey can be done in two ways. Users that have registered to the application can see and access all ongoing surveys matching their user groups. Surveys can also be distributed by sharing a survey specific link that can be used to quickly answer the survey without registering.

2.2 Modeling

In this section, the word model is used to refer to a database model that defines a structure for data being stored to a database. The modeling started by defining the minimal components needed to create a tool for survey management. This included the models for containing information about the users, surveys, questions, and answers. The system was extended by adding the group and evaluation models to fulfill the requirement for more detailed result analysis, and a surveySession model to combine the answers of a single user. The models and their respective relations can be seen in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. The models of the application and their respective relations.

The evaluation model represents the target group of a survey, and it contains one or more groups. The evaluation attached to a survey specifies which groups are able to participate in the survey. The evaluation model was added so that target groups could be easily shared between surveys and recreating a survey with the same target group was simple.

The major question in designing the question model was how to implement the support for multiple sub-questions. It was evaluated whether the question criteria should have its own model, but to keep the questions self-contained it was decided to implement the criteria as a JSON field of the question model. The criteria field is expected to be an array of criteria objects, and a particular structure that can be seen in *Fig. 2*, was designed for the criteria objects.

```

{
  "title": "Importance",
  "description": "",
  "type": "scale",
  "options": { "min":0,"max":5 }
}
  
```

Fig. 2. An example of a criteria object.

The keys “type” and “options” of a criteria object are used to define what kind of question the criteria represent. The two criteria types currently supported are linear scale and multiple

choice. In the client side, the criteria type defines the type of input element rendered for the question, and the options contain the information used to customize the input. For a scale type, the options contain the minimum and maximum values for the input, and for a select type, the options contain the selectable choices, and their respective values. These criteria types were selected, because the questions of the client's evaluation system can be expressed using these two types. The criteria structure was something that the developer team wanted to leave as flexible as possible, so that additional types of criteria could be easily added later on.

2.2.1 Ownership of records

In the beginning, to restrict access to the instances of models that users can interact with, these models contained an owner attribute defining the one user allowed to modify a specific record. The owner attribute was commonly set when a record of a managed model, like a survey or a group, was created. But since the application was originally designed to be used on organizational level, it meant that multiple users would need to access the same records. The owner attribute was removed in favor of a new Permission model used to create ownership defining relations between the user model and any of managed models. Permission model contains the ids of the user and the target instance, and name of the target model. With the Permission model, multiple users can have access to the same managed record. The Permission model was further extended by adding a new attribute defining the allowed operations. With predetermined values for each type of permission, the attribute is used to define whether a user has the permissions to view, edit or delete a specific record.

The tradeoff that comes with the high customizability is that checking the ownership of managed record always involves an additional database query. This also means that retrieving records from the database based on permissions requires the queries going through an extra table. Creating new records also becomes more complicated as it must be guaranteed that no instance of a managed model gets saved without also saving at least one permission record pointing to it. Preventing the database from ending up in an inconsistent state was achieved by wrapping the two insertion operations inside a transaction, meaning that if either of the operations fails, the database will be reverted back to its original state.

2.2.2 Templates

To address the requirement for being able to quickly recreate surveys, two additional models were implemented. The idea is that the new models work as counterparts for the survey and question models, so that a survey can be alternatively saved with its questions as a template and template questions. In the application's current state, templates are considered as public property, and anyone creating a survey has the option to choose an existing template to use as the foundation for the new survey.

2.2.3 Survey sharing

For easier distribution of surveys, a convention for sharing them was developed. The system is based on a new link model built around the idea of a unique key used to access a particular survey. The model is also used to specify which group of the related survey's evaluation the users accessing the survey this way will represent. Alternatively the decision can also be left for the users. A survey can have multiple link objects for different groups at the same time, so that the distribution can be customized to a greater detail.

2.3 Initial technologies

Node.js was selected as the platform for the application, because everyone in the developer team had previously worked with it, and it was suited for the goal of building a modern scalable web application with a large number of third-party modules available.

It was decided early on that a framework was going to be used as a foundation for the application to speed up the development, because time and manpower for the project were limited. To maximize the development speed, Sails was selected as the main framework for the application, because it provided a set of clear guidelines for development, and all the functionality needed to immediately start designing the actual application logic.

2.4 Changing the technology stack

Later in the development it became clear that Sails was the cause for the major problems the team was dealing with. A lot of time was used to create workarounds for the Sails related issues, and in the end, it was decided that the initial product would be finished using the original stack and Sails, but once delivered to the client, another version of the application would be developed with new frameworks for the backend implementations and database operations. The initial version became a test run for the concept, and any features needing to be reworked would get an overhaul in the next version which would replace the original one in production once finished. After delivering the initial version by the deadline, the schedule to develop the next one was more open-ended.

For the final version Koa was selected as the backend framework, because Koa was highly configurable and didn't enforce any strict conventions like Sails that had previously added a limiting effect to the development. Adopting Koa meant redesigning the entire server component, but this way it could be customized for the application's needs.

Due to the high amount of functionality in the front end, React was adopted to the project. React is a library for implementing frontend scripting, and the goal with it was to simplify and increase the maintainability of views that had large amount of scripting attached. The idea of adding SPA (single page application) like functionality to application was considered but dropped in favour of preserving the existing backend logic.

The major task in changing the backend solution was to design the server component and the model system, which were this time not provided directly by the frameworks. Once the foundation was implemented, changing the old code base to use the new system was fairly straightforward.

3 DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Methodology

The development process happened in close cooperation with the clients, and there were meetings about the project every couple of weeks. The meetings were used to inform the clients about the progress made in the development, and because the initial design and requirements for application were relatively loose, time was also spent on polishing the design together with the clients. Since the clients were actively involved in the development process, it was phased so that there were milestones set between every meeting with the goal of having something new to show the clients.

In the early phases of the development certain features were prioritized to create an early working version of the application, so that it would be possible for the clients to actually test the application and better assess the current direction of the development. The feedback from the clients was used throughout the development process to shape application. The production environment for the application was also set up yearly in the development, so that a working version was always be available for the clients for testing purposes.

3.2 Outcome

The application was successfully created in the given period of time, and the survey management part was built successfully to meet the requirements of the client, and the application can be effectively used to create and distribute surveys with multidimensional questions.

The way the users and answerer groups are linked together underwent multiple design changes during the development, and in the end, it was not highly approved by the clients, because of its complexity. The concept of answerer groups was tied so tightly to the application design, that despite it being heavily simplified, it makes the flow much more complex compared to other available survey management tools. The goal of having the application easy to use, was not met in this regard, and should the application be further developed, the enhancement of the usability should one of the priorities.

4 CUSTOMER SERVICE IN REAL LIFE PROJECT

Ever since the early phases of the project, working versions of the application were made available, so that the clients were able to manually test the application during their own time or the regular project meetings. The meetings also included presentations of the application usage and core concepts. To better support the demonstrations and testing, a user manual for the application was created and maintained during the project.

4.1 User guide of the system

The user guide is a documentation used to cover all the essential features of the application, and how to effectively use it. The guide covers everything starting from getting started with the application to detailed descriptions for all of its different views. Because the application design was gradually finalized during the actual development process, the guide had to be frequently updated to cover all the features of the application. *Fig. 3* contains a snippet taken from the user guide describing the view used for editing a user group.

In the edit group page you can:

- Add users to a group
- Remove users from the group
- Give users administrator permissions
- Assign users to an evaluation
- Remove users from an evaluation

Adding users

To add users to a group, start typing the name or username of the user you wish to add in the **Add users to the group** field. When you find the user you are looking for, click it or press enter when the user is highlighted to select it. If the user is not found, it means that they have not signed up.

When all users you wish to add are selected, click the **Add** button next to the search field to add them to the group.

Fig. 3. A snippet from the user guide.

During the project meetings the latest version of the guide was often given to the clients to test if they would be able to properly operate the application only using the guide as a reference. This method of testing often generated practical feedback about both the guide and the application itself, and the method was by far one of the more effective ways of assessing the helpfulness of the guide and the general usability of the application. The long term goal was that an average user would be able to fully utilize the application in survey management just by reading the usage guide.

4.2 Technical documentation for further development

In student driven projects the technical documentation of the delivered artifact is especially important, because the maintenance and any possible further development is likely to be undertaken by different people than the students who originally created it. Without a proper documentation the further development of an existing system is greatly hindered if no one from the original developer team is present, and ultimately it may even lead to the abandonment of the whole application.

In this project the technical documentation is largely built inside the application itself. The flow and the methods are designed and named to be immediately understandable to anyone who has any experience in programming. The documentation system of the programming language is used to clearly express the function signatures, and all the complex functions are associated with comments explaining the general usage and implementation of the function. *Fig. 4* demonstrates how a function used for adding permissions to managed records is documented inside the application by describing its signature and usage.

```
/**
 * Grant one or more rights to a user.
 * @param {User} user the instance of the user record to whom these rights
 *   will be granted
 * @param {Array<string|Number>} rights to allow either as strings or direct
 *   bitmask values
 * @returns {ManagedModel} this instance of chaining
 */
allow(user, ...rights) {
  if(!(user instanceof User) && !user.id) throw new Error('User must be an
    instanceof user or have an id')
  if(!(user instanceof User)) user = new User(user);
  this.permissions.push(new Permission()
    .to(user).for(this).allow(...rights));
  return this;
}
```

Fig. 4. An example function from the application.

The application is based on currently popular frameworks, which is why the developer team refrained from creating a comprehensive technical guide for the application, for to understand the technical implementation of the application, it should be enough to read the general principles of the major frameworks used in the implementation, and go through the conventions and comments found in the actual code base. Instead of explaining the details of the application, the technical documentation focuses on covering on how to get started with the development, and the details of the production environment used to host the application. The documentation gives an overview of the technical implementation, and points out the relevant technologies a developer should be acquainted with to fully understand the details of the implementation. The documentation also contains a step by step guide for setting up the development environment for the application, and a detailed explanation about running the application in production environment.

5 FINAL REMARKS

From a student's perspective the project was an intriguing opportunity to put the skills acquired during courses to a test. Working together on projects with other students is something that almost every course contains, but creating an actual tool for a specific use case in cooperation with a client made the process more challenging. The project required thinking outside the box and combining all the different skills learned during studies, as it was not enough just develop the application and get it up and running. This kind of software project requires taking a multitude of other things into consideration, like how the maintenance is going to be handled and what kind of documentation the users are going to need. All of these things are at least familiar practices or concepts from the courses, but having to apply them to real life project is not always simple, and often requires doing some additional research on the subject.

The project itself was a convenient subject for a thesis, because it was a complex project and it included a lot of different technologies as well as both practical and research oriented work. This made it possible to fine tune the angle of the thesis making it possible to focus on covering the implementation of certain components of the application, or taking a more theoretical approach through covering the research work and design decisions made during the development. The complexity of the project also made it a valid subject for thesis for multiple students, because the subject could be narrowed so precisely that theses would not overlap significantly.

Working closely with a client is an interesting way of working, and it provides both unique benefits and challenges to the development. Having a constant source of feedback is highly beneficial, but it may also prove sometimes to be counterproductive, for it may cause the specifications for the product's features to suddenly change, or introduce new requested features in a rate that can't be sustained. An influx of changes to the design is never desirable, and this emphasizes the importance of having a clear design to follow as early in the development as possible. However, changes and improvements to the design are still a necessity throughout the development if the aim is to create the best possible product, but for the development process to be straightforward, it is best if the changes are kept minimal.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gackenheim, C, Ashworth, T, Jonge, A, (2013), Node.js Recipes. Springer, pp. 1-10.
- [2] Brown, E, (2014), Web Development with Node and Express. Sebastopol, O'Reilly.
- [3] Overview of Blocking vs Non-Blocking [online]. Node.js. URL: <https://nodejs.org/en/docs/guides/blocking-vs-non-blocking/>. Accessed 2 March 2018.
- [4] Young, A, Cantelon, M, Meck, B, (2017), Node.js in action, second edition. Manning Publications.